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Review Paper

Network Pharmacology and Molecular Docking Approaches In Antidiabetic Herbal Drug Research

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disease characterized by elevated blood glucose levels and associated complications, making it a significant global health issue. Although conventional antidiabetic drugs are commonly used, they mainly act on a single target and may lead to side effects, reduced efficacy, and drug resistance over time. In contrast, herbal medicines are increasingly recognized for their therapeutic potential due to their multi-component and multi-target nature, offering a more comprehensive and balanced treatment approach. This review discusses the role of advanced computational techniques such as network pharmacology and molecular docking in antidiabetic herbal drug research. Network pharmacology enables the study of interactions between phytochemicals, biological targets, and disease pathways at a systems level. It involves identification of active compounds, prediction of targets using databases, and analysis of their involvement in biological processes. Molecular docking complements this approach by predicting how bioactive compounds interact with target proteins. It is particularly useful in identifying inhibitors of enzymes like α -amylase and α -glucosidase that regulate blood glucose levels. The integration of these approaches helps identify key phytoconstituents such as diosgenin, apigenin, and rosmarinic acid, along with their associated targets and pathways. Overall, this combined strategy provides deeper insights into the mechanisms of herbal medicines and supports the development of safer and more effective antidiabetic therapies.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic disorder associated with persistent hyperglycemia and

multiple complications^{1,2,45}. Conventional antidiabetic therapies, which generally follow a single-target approach, often show limitations such as side effects, reduced effectiveness, and the

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development of drug tolerance¹. Herbal medicines, on the other hand, provide a promising alternative due to their multi-component and multi-target properties along with comparatively fewer adverse effects^{1,2}. This holistic nature of herbal therapy aligns well with modern drug discovery strategies for complex diseases like DM^{2,9}.

Role of Network Pharmacology in Antidiabetic Herbal Drug Research

Network pharmacology is an advanced systems-based approach that integrates network biology and pharmacology to explore complex interactions among drugs, targets, and diseases^{1,2}. It is particularly suitable for herbal medicines, as they contain multiple bioactive compounds acting on several targets simultaneously^{1,2,9}. This approach helps in understanding the mechanisms of action of traditional medicines and facilitates the identification of new antidiabetic drug candidates^{1,2,8}. It represents a shift from the traditional “one drug–one target” concept to a “multi-component–multi-target” therapeutic model².

Methodological Steps in Network Pharmacology

Data Mining for Compounds and Targets

The first step involves identifying bioactive compounds from medicinal plants and disease-related targets². This is achieved using literature surveys and databases such as TCMSP, PubChem, DrugBank, STITCH, and SwissTargetPrediction^{2,6,8}. Disease-specific databases like GeneCards, TTD, DisGeNET, KEGG, and MalaCards are used to identify targets associated with DM^{4,6}.

Network Construction

After identifying compounds and targets, different interaction networks are constructed, including

herb–compound, compound–target, protein–protein interaction (PPI), and target pathway networks^{2,6,8}. Tools such as Cytoscape and STRING are commonly used^{2,4,8}. In these networks, nodes represent biological entities, while edges represent their interactions⁵.

Network Analysis

These networks are further analyzed to identify important nodes such as hub genes and to understand their biological roles². Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG pathway analyses are used to study molecular functions, biological processes, and cellular components involved in disease mechanisms^{2,4,6}.

Validation of Results

Validation is necessary to confirm predicted targets and mechanisms². While experimental methods (in vitro and in vivo) are essential, computational validation through molecular docking is widely used due to its efficiency and cost-effectiveness².

Molecular Docking Approaches

Molecular docking is a computational method used to predict the interaction between small molecules and target proteins^{2,7,9}. It helps determine binding affinity, interaction strength, and molecular conformation, which are critical for drug discovery⁹.

Applications in Antidiabetic Research

Screening of Enzyme Inhibitors

Enzymes such as α -amylase and α -glucosidase are important therapeutic targets in diabetes⁷. Docking studies help identify inhibitors like curcumin, berberine, catechin, and quercetin that regulate glucose metabolism⁷. Other targets include DPP-4, PTP1B, and GSK3B^{4,25,35}.

Prediction of Bioactivity

Docking helps evaluate the biological activity of plant-derived compounds. For example, resin glycosides have shown α -glucosidase inhibitory activity⁷.

Understanding Multi-Target Effects

Herbal drugs often produce synergistic or additive effects by acting on multiple targets⁹. Docking studies help understand these interactions at the molecular level⁹.

Validation of Network Pharmacology Findings

Docking is used to validate predicted interactions from network pharmacology studies^{2,4,6,24}. For instance, compounds from *Salvia officinalis* such as apigenin and rosmarinic acid showed strong interactions with targets like PTGS2, DPP4, and PPARG4.

Integration of Network Pharmacology and Molecular Docking

The combination of these approaches provides a comprehensive strategy for antidiabetic drug discovery^{2,4}. It overcomes the limitations of single-target approaches and is particularly useful for complex diseases like DM².

Advantages of the Integrated Approach

Holistic Understanding: Explains how multiple compounds interact with multiple targets simultaneously^{1,2}

Identification of Key Compounds: Helps identify major bioactive molecules and their targets^{2,5}

Mechanistic Insights: Explains pathways related to insulin resistance, inflammation, and oxidative stress (PI3K/Akt, AMPK, NF- κ B)^{1,2}

Efficiency: Reduces time and cost in drug discovery through computational tools^{1,2}

Studies on plants like fenugreek and *Polygonatum odoratum* have successfully applied this approach to identify key compounds and mechanisms^{6,22,24,60}.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Although network pharmacology and molecular docking have significantly advanced herbal antidiabetic research, further improvements are needed. Integration with multi-omics technologies (genomics, proteomics, metabolomics) will enhance accuracy^{2,8}. Experimental validation through laboratory and clinical studies remains essential to confirm computational predictions^{2,5,6}.

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

The integration of network pharmacology and molecular docking has greatly improved the understanding of antidiabetic mechanisms of herbal medicines. These approaches have identified key compounds such as diosgenin, apigenin, β -sitosterol, and gypenoside XVII, along with important targets like ESR1, PTGS2, PPARG, and STAT3. These compounds act through multiple pathways including AGE-RAGE, NF- κ B, PPAR, PI3K/Akt, and FoxO1 signaling, leading to improved glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity. Experimental studies support these computational findings, highlighting the potential of herbal medicines in diabetes management. Future research focusing on multi-omics integration and clinical validation will further aid in developing safe and effective antidiabetic therapies.

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